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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Formación de valores y responsabilidad social en jóvenes: una aproximación conceptual*

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Resumen. La investigación se centra en los desafíos apremiantes que supone desarrollar una visión holística del mundo en los estudiantes y fomentar su responsabilidad social, basándose en los valores tradicionales, en el entorno digital moderno. La literatura académica reciente ha observado una mayor atención a los valores de los jóvenes estudiantes y a la influencia de los medios en sus visiones del mundo. Sin embargo, persiste la falta de herramientas eficaces para evaluar estos procesos, lo que exige la mejora del trabajo social y educativo en las universidades. El objetivo de este estudio es desarrollar un enfoque conceptual que permita la aplicación de un método combinado para evaluar y desarrollar las orientaciones valóricas de los estudiantes, basado en el concepto de “héroe cultural” y las tendencias contemporáneas del trabajo social y educativo. El método propuesto, “Héroe del Tiempo”, combina cuestionarios y experimentos: los estudiantes crean un “avatar de héroe” mediante el análisis de contenido de imágenes mediáticas significativas de sus propias biografías. Este enfoque permite identificar los valores tradicionales e imágenes mediáticas clave que influyen en la visión del mundo de los estudiantes, así como las contradicciones de valores. En particular, la mayoría de los encuestados identificaron un conflicto entre los valores materiales y espirituales, que debe tenerse en cuenta al planificar el trabajo educativo. Los resultados del estudio confirman que la educación social orientada a valores, teniendo en cuenta las imágenes mediáticas relevantes, fomenta eficazmente la visión holística del mundo y la responsabilidad social de los estudiantes.

Palabras clave: cosmovisión de los estudiantes, valores tradicionales, imágenes de los medios de comunicación, responsabilidad social, trabajo social y educativo.

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Formation of values and social responsibility among young people: a conceptual approach

Abstract. The research problem is related to urgent tasks of forming an integral worldview of students and developing their social responsibility on the basis of traditional values under the conditions of the contemporary digital media environment. Recent scholarly literature shows increased attention to the values of student youth and to the influence of the media on their worldview, yet there is still a lack of effective tools for diagnosing these processes, which necessitates improving social and educational work at universities. The aim of this study is to develop a conceptual approach that would make it possible to apply a combined methodology for diagnosing and shaping the value orientations of student youth, based on the concept of the “cultural hero” and contemporary trends in social and educational work. The proposed “Hero of Time” methodology combines a questionnaire survey and an experiment: students create a “hero avatar” by carrying out content analysis of media images that are significant for them from their own media biography. This approach makes it possible to identify key traditional values and media images that influence the worldview of students, as well as to record value conflicts. In particular, a conflict between material and spiritual values was revealed in most respondents, which must be taken into account when planning educational work. The results of the study confirm that value oriented social and educational work that takes into account relevant media images ensures the effective formation of an integral worldview of students and of their social responsibility.

Keywords: students’ worldview, traditional values, media images, social responsibility, social and educational work.

INTRODUCTION

Consideration of issues related to the organization of social and educational work in higher educational institutions and to the formation of values, worldview, and social responsibility of student youth should begin with the introduction of basic concepts. According to the Federal Law “On Education in the Russian Federation”, upbringing is defined as

«activity aimed at personal development, the formation in students of diligence, a responsible attitude toward work and its results, the creation of conditions for self determination and socialization of students on the basis of sociocultural, traditional Russian spiritual and moral values and the rules and norms of behavior accepted in Russian society in the interests of the individual, the family, society and the state, the formation in students of a sense of patriotism, civic consciousness, respect for the memory of the defenders of the Fatherland and the feats of the Heroes of the Fatherland, for law and order, for working people and the older generation, mutual respect, a careful attitude toward the cultural heritage and traditions of the multinational people of the Russian Federation, nature and the environment» (State Duma of the Federal Assembly of the Russian Federation, 2012).

This extensive definition describes the processes of socialization, inculturation, and civic identification (Sergeeva et al., 2025), which require special attention in social and educational work with young people (Markheim & Lukyanova, 2023; Babina & Utusikov, 2024; Letova, 2024; Vassilchenko, 2024).

In this study, youth is understood as student youth, that is, students as a group of people aged from 14 to 35 who are receiving professional education in specialized institutions of basic education and who are actively undergoing the stage of socialization and inculturation, including through organized social and educational activities (Kurgansky et al., 2025; Usmanova et al., 2025).

At the same time, it should be noted that patriotic and civic education in particular makes it possible to simplify the process of identification and the formation of a unified and stable world view (Sergeeva & Pitul'ko, 2023; Sidorov, 2025). Researchers note that “patriotic education helps students to form a sense of commitment and identification with the country, promotes solidarity and unity in society, and forms basic civic responsibility and participation in the life of their country” (Kochesokov, 2022; Parma, 2024).

The problem of destructive informational influences remains significant, as does the fact that universities are often absorbed in their own formal reality while falling out of the sphere of informal communication (Danilova, 2024; Gazizova et al., 2025). Yet it is precisely informal communication that makes it possible to construct a subjective picture of the world from elements of personal experience (Titova et al., 2025). Here it is possible to rely on the theory of intersubjectivity (Husserl, 2010). Its representations are accessible to us in the symbolism of texts (Blumer, 2017). Textuality, in turn, ensures the functioning of the media field and the media system. Work aimed at forming an intersubjective picture of the world that takes into account value orientations and shapes an integral worldview is one of the leading tasks of higher education as a sociocultural system (Khammatova et al., 2021; Pashkurov et al., 2023; Mamedova et al., 2025).

In recent years, a number of studies have paid particular attention to the formation of the values of student youth (Dulina et al., 2022; Ivanova & Tazov, 2022; Malinin et al., 2022; Kazenina & Sakharova, 2023; Pokrovskaja et al., 2024). A certain body of research is devoted to examining issues of civic identity and worldview through the prism of the media (Dunas, 2022; Dunas et al., 2022; Nigmatullina, 2022; Zvereva & Khvorova, 2022; Parma, 2024; Goncharenko et al., 2025). Modeling stable worldview categories that make it possible to pass effectively through socialization and subsequent adaptation in a specific professional environment cannot be imagined without studying the value portrait of the student (Shabalina et al., 2024). One of its key elements is the appropriation and representation of archetypal images of cultural heroes and new heroes.

At the national level, relevant surveys are conducted, for example the VCIOM survey “Heroes of 2020” (VCIOM, 2020)). In the student environment, surveys remain an effective tool, although a certain fatigue of respondents from filling out a large number of questionnaires is noticeable. The application of new methodologies is therefore required (Kalashnikov et al., 2023; Grudtsina et al., 2025). There is a need to develop specific instruments aimed at identifying the existing set of value orientations and at programming generalized cultural media images, including heroic and mythological ones (Polyakova et al., 2018; Chernova et al., 2025). This is also one

of the most important tasks of social and educational work with students in higher education institutions (Akhmetshin et al., 2025a).

METHODS

As part of the study, work was carried out to develop a methodology for researching students' values. The aim of this methodology is to describe the main value orientations of a selected group of student youth and the main worldview trends within it. The objectives are: 1) to identify stable images of heroes that influence the formation of worldview, 2) to analyze data on the elements of the picture of the world, 3) to compile a general portrait of the group. The implementation of the methodology is carried out in the form of an experiment. The main methods are a survey and content analysis. The working title of the methodology is "Hero of Time".

The study and the development of the methodology were conducted in two stages. At each stage, student focus groups and expert discussions with teachers from various fields of the Herzen State Pedagogical University of Russia were held in 2025. Each of the four focus groups included 10 students from the first to the fourth year of study in different educational programs. In total, 40 students took part in the focus groups, with equal representation of male and female students. Participation in the focus groups was voluntary. Two focus groups were formed from first- and second-year bachelor's students, and two from third- and fourth-year students. The participants represented various humanities disciplines. Their age ranged from 18 to 25 years. Five teachers took part in four expert discussions, representing the fields of Advertising and Public Relations, Cultural Studies, Sociology, Philosophy, and Pedagogy. The composition of participants did not change during the expert discussions. In the further testing of the methodology, the students who had participated in its development did not take part, since their familiarity with the structure of the methodology could have affected the representativeness of the data.

At the first stage, the main issues of organizing the methodology were considered: 1) what are the goals of the survey and the content analysis, 2) how will the sources for content analysis be selected, 3) how can the survey and content analysis be linked and the experimental form of the study ensured. These questions were posed to the participants of the student focus groups. The answers obtained were then analyzed and presented at the beginning of the expert discussions with teachers, who were expected to evaluate them and propose professional recommendations on the issues identified. In total, two focus groups and two expert discussions were conducted. As a result of the analysis of the data obtained, the following foundations for the further conduct of the study were formulated.

First, the main goal of the survey is to diagnose students' internal assessments of various relevant worldview categories and their reflection on them. The content analysis is aimed at creating a general portrait of the "hero of time" using such a tool as the client avatar.

Second, the sources for content analysis must meet certain criteria. The period of media consumption of the source should fall within the period from 2010 to 2025. The starting point was chosen as the year when the social network Instagram entered the market. Instagram is owned by Meta, which is recognized as an extremist organization and banned in the Russian Federation, and its emergence fundamentally changed the media landscape and the dynamics of

social network use. In addition, it was during this period that the processes of socialization and inculturation of contemporary students were actively taking place. Furthermore, the source must be known to a wide audience within the national media system of Russia. The analysis of foreign sources and sources in a foreign language that are popular among Russian consumers is allowed. The source must contain a description of a hero or character, descriptions of individual elements of the image or references to it, and must be familiar and relevant to the student. The analyzed hero must either be the main character or be mentioned at least three times in the source.

Third, it was noted that a separate group of students should participate in the experiment. Under the guidance of a teacher, this group independently carries out content analysis and creates a hero avatar, and then takes part in the survey. The subject of the researcher's analysis is the constructed hero avatar and the survey responses. In this case, the researcher gains access both to sources in various areas of spiritual culture and media that are relevant and selected by the students themselves, and to their assessment of leading media images of heroes that are genuinely important for the selected group.

At the first stage, within the framework of these qualitative studies, the structure of the future methodology was developed and the main levels of its implementation were identified, united in a single process of conducting the experiment. The results of the first stage of the study and the development of the methodology are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Structure of the “Hero of Time” methodology.

Process	Level	Tasks
Preparation	1	Selection of the student group, conduct of an introductory briefing, introduction of the rules of content analysis.
Experiment	2	Selection by students of source domains, division into subgroups, creation of a list of sources by domains.
	3	Description by students of the general characteristics of the selected domain.
	4	Analysis of the selected sources within the specified period. Identification of the main images of heroes.
	5	Creation of a “hero avatar” by domains. Merging of subgroups and creation of a general hero avatar.
	6	Participation of the group in the survey.
Analysis	7	Final analysis of the data obtained by the researcher.

At the second stage, the substantive aspects of the content analysis and the survey were examined. Within the framework of two focus groups and two expert discussions, the main survey themes were developed on the basis of various elements of the media image of the new cultural hero.

The respondents were asked to answer the question of what this image consists of and what the main problems associated with it are. As a result of the analysis of the data obtained, it was established that the key themes in this context are the following: the external portrait of the hero, ideas and values, lifestyle, education and profession, romance and marriage, the

“fathers and children” theme, success, fears of the hero of the time and his or her desires, and the question of what is “bad” or “good”. Final themes were also identified: who the hero is and how to describe him or her, that is, the hero avatar. In addition, within the framework of these qualitative studies, the leading domains for source selection were identified: social networks, video services, television, film and TV series, literature, advertising, journalism (press), visual arts, music, and performing arts. These themes and domains formed the basis of the content analysis matrix presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2. Content analysis matrix.

Domain	Social networks, video services, television, film and TV series, literature, advertising, journalism (press), visual arts, music and performing arts.
Years	2010-2025.
General characteristics of domain development	Main tendencies and trends
List of sources (viewed materials)	Numbered list of sources, publication details, statistics
Answers to the main questions	External portrait of the hero of the time. Ideas and values of the hero of the time. Lifestyle of the hero of the time. Role of the profession of the hero of the time. Romance in the life of the hero of the time. Attitude of the hero of the time toward marriage. The “fathers and children” conflict for the hero of the time. Importance of success and its manifestations for the hero of the time. Fears of the hero of the time. Which action is good and which action is bad for the hero of the time?
Conclusions	Construction of the hero avatar (by analogy with the client avatar method).
Main processes	Selection of sources, decoding of images by parameters, visualization.

During the expert discussions, it was noted that in order to conduct an effective worldview analysis it is necessary to link the topics of the content analysis with the topics of the final survey, which was done. For each topic, clarifying questions were developed. The main task of this survey is to consider not a group but a subjective picture of the hero of the time and to create an individual hero avatar through reflection on one’s own image. It is precisely the comparative analysis of the subjective and the social worldview models, the identification of leading images and characters, relevant sources and their representations in cultural and creative industries that makes it possible to understand the values of a group of students. The structure of the survey by main topics with clarifying questions is presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3. Structure of the survey.

Main topics	Clarifying questions
Introductory questions	How old are you? Indicate your gender. If you are working, in which field?
External portrait	Describe the clothing style you like most. How important are appearance and beauty of a person to you? What is more important for you: naturalness or following trends?
Ideas and values	Write three words that best describe your value system. What is more important for you: justice or mercy? Why? What is more important for you: money or feelings? Why? What is more important for you: popularity or professionalism? Why? What is more important for you: popularity or money? Why? How respectful are you toward those who hold opposite views?
Lifestyle	How dependent are you on social networks and digital technologies? How do you feel about rest and entertainment? How do you prefer to rest?
Education	How important is education for you? Why are you studying or why did you study? Which professional qualities do you consider most important? List three to five. What motivates you in professional activity? Do you consider it important to constantly improve your professional skills? If yes, why?
Romance and marriage	Are you a romantic person? For you, love is... What is more important: romance or success? Why do people enter into marriage? In your opinion, how has the attitude toward marriage changed in the modern world? What is most important for you in marriage?
The "fathers and children" problem	Do you learn anything from the older generation? In which spheres of life does the generation gap, in your opinion, manifest itself most acutely today?
Success	What is success for you? Is success important for you? How do you demonstrate your success to others? How strongly do you strive for recognition and fame?
Fears	What do you fear most? How do you cope with your fears?
Bad or good	Give an example of an action that you consider absolutely good. Why? Give an example of an action that you consider absolutely bad. Why? Could you justify violating moral norms in order to achieve a goal?
Desires	What do you want most? What do you strive for?
Hero	A hero is... Who is a hero for you now in everyday life? Imagine that you are a writer. Describe the hero of our time for your reader

Comparative analysis of the experimental data is carried out by identifying trend based frequent responses and by comparing group and individual hero avatars. Frequency analysis is performed using Microsoft Excel tools, and comparative analysis of the avatars is conducted, among other things, using generative artificial intelligence models, primarily YandexGPT by Yandex. The result of the content analysis in the form of a hero avatar is common to the group, while the specific questionnaire responses are anonymous. The results of the data analysis are not disclosed to the participants in the experiment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The developed methodology makes it possible to (Mikhaylova, 2024): 1) identify sources of spiritual culture that are important for the student group and images of heroes of the time, both artistic and real (Garaganov, 2024), 2) create a general group portrait of the hero with a description of his or her values, worldview and aspirations, 3) determine on this basis the range of value related problems, such as uncertainty of the picture of the world, differentiation of values within the group, destructive worldview elements, and others, 4) study the individual picture of the world and find in it similarities with the general worldview of the group, 5) assess the main risks of educational activity.

Based on the analysis of the data obtained, it is possible to build communication with a selected group of students in the context of three to five shared constructive values, taking into account relevant media images, and to further develop this value framework by instilling new professional and supra professional values, introducing new images of cultural heroes that are consonant with the goals of the university's educational activity (Akhmetshin et al., 2025b), and developing students' internal motivation to study by linking it with an image of future subjective well being that determines satisfaction with their education (Vaslavskiy & Vaslavskaya, 2022; Togaibayeva et al., 2023; Kryucheva & Tolstoukhova, 2024). All the technologies described above should be used positively in educational work, cutting off destructive values, destructive heroes and a fragmented worldview (Abdullayev et al., 2024; Serebrennikova, 2024). For example, the first experience of applying the methodology showed, through the use of cross checking questions in the survey, that more than 60 percent of respondents revealed a conflict between material and spiritual values. These data must be taken into account in educational work with this group.

Thus, social and educational work whose foundation is value analysis and which perceives and works with relevant media images within the architecture of informal reality will effectively form an integral worldview of students (Shichkin et al., 2024).

The methodology presented represents a comprehensive analysis of the values of student youth and its individual groups in the organization of educational work at a university. This study was aimed at creating such a methodology. The "Hero of Time" methodology was developed through qualitative sociological research, including focus groups with students themselves and expert discussions with teachers from various disciplines. It is based on conducting an experiment with a particular group of student youth. Within this framework, students independently perform content analysis of cultural sources and construct a unified image, the hero avatar. In addition, a final survey is conducted, the purpose of which is to identify individual heroic images through the prism of reflection.

The final analysis is comparative. It evaluates stable images, values and worldviews of the student group and of individual participants within it. This allows the researcher to form a comprehensive understanding of the worldview, of media images and values that are relevant to students and embedded in them, to compile a database of leading sources of spiritual culture (Lykova et al., 2023; Platonova et al., 2025). The researcher can also assess various destructive elements in the axiological framework of students, in their heroes and in their worldview as a whole, as well as evaluate the degree of worldview differentiation (Gabidullina et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

Within the framework of social and educational work at a university, it is possible to form an integral and constructive professional and supra professional worldview and to increase motivation for learning and engagement in scientific activity, which constitutes the mission of this type of activity.

To enhance the effectiveness of social and educational work, it is necessary to intensify the processes of diagnostics and of creating and representing informal reality within the activities of universities. This requires new tools based on quantitative and qualitative analysis and on an experimental foundation.

The research materials and its theoretical framework can be used by higher education institutions in their work. In particular, they can be incorporated into programs for organizing social and educational practices with students, within which activities aimed at forming values, worldview, and social responsibility of student youth will be implemented.

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